

Insect Juvenile Hormone Analogues. Part-XXIII. Synthesis of Some Functionalised Analogues of Long Chain Aliphatic Acid Amides and Their Juvenile Hormone Activity

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4,8-Dimethyl-3(E),7-nonadienoic acid, 5,9-dimethyl-4(E),8-decadienoic acid and geranylthioacetic acid are condensed with various anilines to furnish corresponding amides (9-13), (14-18) and (19-23). These amides on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid gave epoxides (24-28) and (29-33), and sulphoxides (34-38). All the compounds synthesised were tested for their JH activity on *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus*.

LITERATURE survey reveals^{1,2} that amides derived from *para*-substituted anilines and geraniol exhibit remarkable biological activity on hemipteran species. In this communication, we report the synthesis of a few amides by increasing the aliphatic chain length, introduction of sulphur atom in the chain, and check their effect on JH activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus*. Amides were prepared from 4,8-dimethyl-3(E),7-nonadienoic acid (1), 5,9-dimethyl-4(E),8-decadienoic acid (2) and geranylthioacetic acid (3) with various *para*-substituted anilines (4-8). Modification has been effected in each series at the terminal double bond to prepare their corresponding oxirane derivatives. 4,8-Dimethyl-3(E),7-nonadienoic acid^a (1), 5,9-dimethyl-4(E),8-decadienoic acid^b (2) and geranylthioacetic acid^c (3) were prepared by the procedure reported in the literature. All these acids were condensed^d with aniline (4), *p*-chloroaniline (5), *p*-methylaniline (6), *p*-methoxyaniline (7) and *p*-ethoxyaniline (8) in the presence of triethylamine and POCl₃ in dry methylene chloride at 0° to give their respective amides (9-13), (14-18) and (19-23). Amides (9-13) and (14-18), on epoxidation^e with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in dry methylene chloride at 0° yielded their corresponding mono-epoxy derivatives (24-28) and (29-33). Amides (19-23) having sulphur atom in their structures gave sulphoxides (34-38) instead of epoxides.

JH activity: All the compounds (tlc pure) were tested for their JH activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus* according to the procedure reported in the literature^{7,8}. Farnesyl methyl ether was used as the standard reference (JH score=4.00)⁹. JH activity indices result of the various compounds is listed in Table 1. Activity indices reports that

TABLE 1—JH ACTIVITY OF VARIOUS COMPOUNDS
SYNTHESISED

Number of insects used=10, dose=1% in acetone (6 μl)

Compd. no.	Dead	Activity response					Activity index
		0	1	2	3	4	
9	0	5	0	1	4	0	1.4
10	1	7	0	0	2	0	0.66
11	0	2	0	1	6	1	2.4
12	0	5	1	0	4	0	1.3
13	0	7	0	0	3	0	0.9
24	0	0	1	1	1	7	8.4
25	0	4	0	2	3	1	1.7
26	0	0	1	1	7	1	2.8
27	0	5	1	0	4	0	1.3
28	0	5	0	1	4	0	1.4
14	0	6	1	1	2	0	0.9
15	0	4	2	1	1	2	1.5
16	1	5	1	1	2	0	1.0
17	2	6	0	1	1	0	0.62
18	0	7	1	1	1	0	0.60
29	0	1	1	0	8	0	2.5
30	0	6	0	0	4	0	1.2
31	2	1	0	3	8	4	2.87
32	0	6	0	2	2	0	1.0
33	0	3	0	0	2	5	2.6
19	1	5	1	1	2	0	1.0
20	0	0	2	0	1	7	8.8
21	1	0	0	0	4	5	8.55
22	0	8	0	0	2	0	0.6
23	2	1	1	0	4	2	2.63
34	1	6	1	0	0	2	1.1
35	0	0	0	0	3	7	3.7
36	0	0	0	0	5	5	3.5
37	2	5	0	0	3	0	1.12
38	0	1	0	0	6	3	3.0

epoxy derivatives are more active than their parent compounds. Spectral data of all the synthesised compounds are in consistence with their structures.

4, 9, 14, 19, 24, 29, 34 R = Phenyl
 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35 R = *p*-Cl-Phenyl
 6, 11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36 R = *p*-CH₃-Phenyl
 7, 12, 17, 22, 27, 32, 37 R = *p*-OCH₃-Phenyl
 8, 13, 18, 23, 28, 33, 38 R = *p*-OC₂H₅-Phenyl

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 60-80°. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were recorded in CCl₄ on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Tlc was done using silica gel (N.C.L.) impregnated with 13% binder. Unless mentioned otherwise column chromatography was done using commercial alumina of Brockmann activity (B.D.H./E. Merck).

N-Phenyl-2(2,6-dimethyl-1(*E*),5-heptadienyl)acetamide (9): To a stirred solution of 4,8-dimethyl-3(*E*),7-nonadienoic and the acid (1; 2.00 g), triethylamine (1.10 g) and aniline (1.03 g) in methylene chloride (50 ml) was added a solution of POCl₃ (1.69 g) in methylene chloride (20 ml) at 0°. Triethylamine (2.2 g) was then added and the reaction mixture was stirred for additional 30 min at 0° and 30 min at room temperature. The contents were poured on water and the organic layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and then again with water and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂. Evaporation of the solvent followed by chromatography over neutral alumina, with petroleum ether-ether (19 : 1) as eluent, gave the

amide (9) (1.9 g, 70%) (Found : C, 79.35 ; H, 9.00. C₁₇H₂₃NO requires C, 79.33 ; H, 9.01%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ 3300, 3250, 3160, 3100, 2950, 2890, 1600, 1550, 1510, 1450, 1425, 1390, 1300, 1260, 1195, 1185, 1110, 1090, 1045, 910, 845, 800, 755 and 745 cm⁻¹ ; δ 1.6 (9H, m, allylic Me), 2.1 (4H, m, CH₂-CH₂-C=), 3.1 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, =CH-CH₂-CO-NH-), 5.2-5.6 (2H, m, olefinic H), 7.05-7.65 (5H, m, Ar-H) and 7.8 (1H, bs, -CO-NH-).

Similarly amides (10-13), (14-18) and (19-23) were prepared (yield 65-78%) by treating the corresponding acids with different substituted anilines. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

N-Phenyl-2(2,6-dimethyl-5,6-epoxy-1(*E*)-heptenyl)acetamide (24): *m*-Chloroperbenzoic acid (1.5 g) in the methylene chloride (20 ml) was added at 0° to a solution of (9; 2.00 g) in methylene chloride (50 ml) and stirring was continued for 30 min. Then ice-cold water was added. The organic layer separated, was washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and the solvent was distilled off. The residue was chromatographed over florisil using petroleum ether as eluent to give 24 (1.49 g, 70%) (Found : C, 75.60 ; H, 8.48. C₁₇H₂₃NO₂

requires C, 74.60 ; H, 8.48%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ 3300, 3250, 3160, 2990, 2950, 2890, 1660, 1550, 1500, 1450, 1390, 1260, 1195, 1185, 1110, 1090, 1045, 910, 845, 800, 755 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.25 (6H, saturated Me), 1.3-1.85 (5H, olefinic methyl and epoxy $-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.25 (2H, t, J 9 Hz, epoxy $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 2.60 (1H, t, epoxy $-H$), 3.15 (2H, d, $=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{NH}$), 5.35 (1H, olefinic H), 7.0-7.65 (5H, m, Ar- H) and 7.85 (1H, CONH).

Amides (10-13) and (14-18) were treated with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid to yield the respective oxiranes (25-28) and (29-33). In case of amides (19-23), sulphoxides (34-38) were prepared instead of corresponding oxiranes. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

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